

DICTIONARIES ARE TREASURES OF THE NATION

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Abstract. This article talks about dictionaries and their role in human life. The difficulty of creating a dictionary, the specific principles of creating dictionary articles are covered.

Key words: dictionary, dictionary article, accumulation, language, meaning.

One of the sages said: "The real treasure of every household is a dictionary." In fact, dictionaries are an incomparable bridge that contributes to the transmission of language from generation to generation. They are a mirror that reflects how beautiful and rich our language is. At the same time, it is impossible to imagine science and education without dictionaries.

Our President Sh.M. Mirziyoev is leading a number of reforms to ensure the development of our native language. Including 2020 On October 20, the President's decree No. PF-6084 "On measures to further develop the Uzbek language in our country and improve the language policy" was signed(1). Based on this decree, the concept of further development of the Uzbek language and improvement of the language policy in 2020-2030 was developed. In the program created based on this concept, the priority task was to develop the Uzbek language educational lexicography network, to create modern, new generation educational dictionaries and to improve the national terminological system by fields by creating their electronic forms. In order to ensure the implementation of the tasks defined in this decree, a number of dictionaries and a number of studies on lexicology are being created.

Dictionaries, first of all, serve to fulfill the function of the language as an

accumulator (accumulate from Latin - to accumulate (3)). Any dictionary is created based on several steps. Dictionary creators serve as the basis for all lexicographic decisions, from choosing the type and form of writing from the dictionary, to choosing words, types of information, choosing a place for information (for example, in a dictionary article or in an appendix). does. Dictionary articles are formed on the basis of two stages. The initial stage is a communication-oriented stage, which includes processes such as the development, revision and translation of a text aimed at the interpretation of a particular word. The next stage, which determines the level of knowledge orientation of the dictionary article, deals with situations related to the reception (comprehension) of the text. In this case, it is important that the dictionary serves to obtain specific knowledge about a certain thing. It is important that dictionaries provide the maximum amount of information about a given concept in a minimal way.

Summarizing, sorting, and commenting on words requires special knowledge, talent, and work. The famous philologist of the Middle Ages, Justus Scaliger, said: "If someone is condemned to hard work and suffering, let him ignore the hard work of blacksmiths and miners and order him to compile a dictionary: this the work itself is the most difficult of all difficulties", he said. These sentences alone show how difficult it is to create a vocabulary.

Nowadays, many prefer to use electronic dictionaries. Electronic dictionaries created for mobile phones are becoming more popular than traditional printed dictionaries.

It would be appropriate to conclude our opinion with the following sentences of the famous Uzbek writer Pirimkul Kadirov: All the power of the language is related to its creation and enrichment in the vernacular and in the labor process. When people do a lot of work, they feel the need to talk to each other and communicate through words. One generation explains its work

experience to another generation through words. In this way, language riches created hundreds and thousands of years ago enrich the spiritual world of people from generation to generation. Due to the fact that the language was created in the process of labor, its main source and main roots, the main wealth are also in the working people (2). Collecting such linguistic resources from among the people, polishing them and passing them on to the next generation is an honorable and urgent task at the same time!

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